

Incremental Revitalization: Abandoned Industrial Buildings

Alexandros Postekkis, Petros Lapithis

University of Nicosia, Department of Architecture, Sustainable Architecture Unit, Nicosia, Cyprus

Introduction

Industrialization has been a major chapter of the world development, affecting culturally, socially, economically as well as architecturally the life of the previous, mechanization, 20th century citizens. Industrial revolution had a great impact taking over the whole world, but its great growth also demanded a constant increase of factories shaping the industrial character of the era. The urban environment was introduced to new building typologies of areas shaped by the image of factories where great public interest was attracted for working plus living¹. This radical development was the beginning of the great industrial cities, equal to the concept of a "social condenser" within the greater rural network. The idea of these building's generation was a result of a fast growing development creating a productive manufacturing system, which activated the socioeconomic system. As the interest in buying was higher, more and more factories were being built through the years but unfortunately, wrong management and failing economy in many regions of the world, resulted to the decline or even the death of Industrial Buildings in a worldwide scale². As a result, the "death" of business and the closing of industrial units, demolitions or in some cases the sealing of factories was bound to happen.

Due to the fact of no more financial recourses, factories with great importance regarding their offerings to the 20th century society and in some cases with their dominant architectural characteristic style, started losing their value as social condensers as well as their original value of production and in addition, their importance of maintenance and care. These buildings turned into neutral spaces, which posed an urban problem of non-used structure around the urban regions. Also, these structures underlined the importance of preserving architectural heritage during the past few years. This process of preservation of memory and identity of a building or neighbourhoods and public spaces³ is a greatly supported and promoted process of re-establishment through generous financial and other motives, but also from private initiatives of individuals who have learnt to respect and enhance the value of architectural forms of the past⁴. By using the example of Duisburg Park in Germany, along with others, a showcase of important techniques of building function memory maintenance will be explored for further use in my studio proposal.

The aim of this paper is to explain the importance of re-using valuable, un-used buildings like outdated factories and revitalizing them by bringing them to the 21st century while at the same time, keeping a piece of their memory and their important contribution through their course of "life". The new users of the transformed building or site as well as the wider public will not only see the romantic and nostalgic side of a revitalized industrial building, but also its functional and financial contribution in the modern way of life where through sustainability of re-use and respecting something old and neglected, can be brought back to life for something new and exciting⁵.

Revitalization of Industrial Buildings

There are two major attitudes towards an old building revitalization; firstly the maintenance of its previous character and memory through restoring techniques where the original structure and the new one come together in harmony and respect and, oppositely, the approach where there is a complete building re-use without any references to the structure's original purpose⁶. Restoration is a great architectural domain of development through the centuries and the aim has always been the possible life expansion of important buildings as well as their value to society and the culture. There is no doubt that an abandoned superannuated factory, where technology and style have been outdated, is a challenge but at the same time, a fascinating concept that challenges the architect, designer or planer to protect its original, historical and emotional value and most importantly its unique identity⁷.

Through the years, a constant increase of non-used factory buildings worldwide and the neglecting attitude towards the previous functioning structure, poses a question of what can we actually do with all these non used but possibly valuable spaces? The future of this building is questioned; how we should treat this condition in order to revitalize the structures once more and incorporate them into the living organism of the urban fabric and at the same time, maintain its memory as cultural heritage. Several approaches have been explored through

the years, stating from two major categories of industrial building's re-use; the first being its transition into a museum or the complete alteration to incorporate new uses. Both approaches will be explained in more detail.

Museums of Industrial Archaeology

It is important then, to understand the architectural and memory value of these buildings towards society and its surroundings. Since an industrial building becomes not only a landmark for a place but also a landmark in history, it could be transformed into a museum. Then it becomes subject of investigation of industrial archaeology. As long as it fulfills the criteria and the requirements, it becomes part of the cultural heritage of a society under the protection of the state⁸. This will reflect the culture of a civilization and its evolution through the time. Nevertheless, this chain of cultural samples should be complete with the preservation of industrial buildings and focus their interest as industrial museums of their technological and technical equipment. As result, this building can inhabit only a specific use so this could be only the "museum in and of itself"⁹.

Although the new use of industrial building to an industrial museum is preserving the existing building, this also requires a series of additions and improvements either to its structural system or to its infrastructure. These improvements will ensure and create the proper conditions for the building in order to accommodate the new uses, according to the correct requirements. Some of these changes could be the structural and anti-seismic reinforcement, architectural changes that will support not only the new functional requirements but also the mechanical ones and generally provide to the building the support to function as a contemporary museum which most probably is not supported by the existing situation¹⁰.

The task of the architectural interaction to the existing fabric of the building should be the distinct contrast with the existing and genuine parts of the building. In a way, we treat the building as a monument in order to avoid any misunderstandings and confusions of the users, in the future use between the existing structure and the new additional parts.

It will be unfair to take for granted that all abandoned, industrial buildings should be preserved as cultural heritage museums. The reason is not only financial. Preserving and transforming all industrial buildings into museums will create a wasteful chain of building reducing the value and interest of those who really worthy to be museums. The evaluation and the record of an industrial building, in order to be preserved, should be executed under specified criteria that will result to the selection of few representative examples of each period with main aim the preservation of the industrial equipment. This will result to a complete chain of industrial archaeology samples that constitutes the history of a place¹¹.

Small Museum coexist with new uses

The luck of the abandoned industrial buildings that cannot be reutilized or even restored as museums is always architecturally questioned with regards to their integration into the urban fabric and contemporary life. This is the majority of the cases where, if they become museums, they will repeat themselves in a boring way and also it would very wasteful for the state to support such a strategy for all of them. Nevertheless, these cases are treated with a different way that tries to balance between the museum and the new uses. The solution is given with the restoration of part of the mechanical equipment in combination of the reuse of the building fabric with complete new uses. This cohabitation of these two components will give the result of a small museum that is decorated with the new functions within the space of an industrial building¹².

Revitalized Industrial Buildings

One can wonders if there is any sense to have a spread exhibition of mechanical equipment around the restored building where the practical approach should be to house new functions that these buildings can offer as a building fabric. The revitalization of an industrial building is the last choice to save industrial buildings in new uses. The reason for not demolishing them completely, in order to give their place to a new contemporary building for the needs of the city, is their architectural value and their importance as symbols of memory, landmarks¹³.

Therefore, their architectural interest is concentrated in their industrial landscape context. The buildings that give character to area around them and will always recall the memory and history of the production with no need to educate the public with museum approaches¹⁴. Thereby the reuse of an industrial landscape should aim

to conserve the memory of the place, taking account that this place should function as a “landmark”. We should be careful, however, not to restore an industrial building and settling it as a decorative object within its urban context.

Dilemma

Should we maintain the cultural heritage that is incorporated in the structure of a historical building at any cost, or should we allow the domination of new use and structure. A balance between heritage and the economic and utilitarian value should exist and be succeeded. But where precisely this line is found ? Each building has a different value, problems and the occasions of heritage. Accordingly, each individual building should be judged differently¹⁵. While setting any criteria of judging a building for its cultural value according either to its architectural or memory value, we should consider in parallel the finance and the feasibility of bringing a building into life again.

However, one can wonder then what is the difference between taking an industrial building and transforming it into any kind of public or private building without any reference to its predecessor, and demolishing it and constructing it from the beginning. A radical transformation of an industrial building from one day to another could only create questions and misunderstandings to the people that until now are related to and conceive this building as having a specific use and character¹⁶. Memory of a place is subjective and can go through changes as one lives and experiences life. But if that memory is harassed drastically, it turns into a mistreatment of a place and is probably undesirable. The question that this paper is called to answer is what is the balance between the transformation of a building into its new condition while at the same time establishing a harmony between memory, cost efficiency and feasibility.

Incremental Revitalization of Industrial Buildings

Incremental transformation of industrial buildings is an approach that shifts between the two ideas of either reusing an industrial building fabric incorporating new uses or demolishing it and construct a new one. Incremental transformation manages to create the proper conditions for the revitalization of an industrial building in order to succeed not only to incorporate new uses through new construction but also to relate to its predecessor use and function. Nevertheless, this will result to a thriving adaptive program for a ‘place’ and its memory, thus it will be related to the previous function so the users can easily reference and accept its transformation not as an assault, but as a further development as life goes on¹⁷. Consequently, the new construction will be accepted as the ‘tool’ of the memory’s development. However, it should be kept in mind that this is not a change but a transformable development that should be executed step by step so people can be part of this procedure and finally accept it.

Methodology

This strategy deals with a design of step by step execution from the inside to the outside, like a worm eating an apple from the inside to the outside and finally reveals the reality of the inner space. The idea describes the transformation of the building structure and functions, from the inside to the outside incrementally, where eventually the building, in a long term time, will completely change. One could describe this gesture as an expansion of new functions by recycling the existing ones of a building in stages, which will eventually be revealed. The result will be a transformed new building, like an apocalypse through the years and simultaneously a method of acceptance by the users.

Memory as Design Strategy

Memory was always a property that was related with architecture where as a man experiences a space, all the information related to the space is stored, retained and recalled into his mind. A relationship then is created between the user and a place or building, that can be described each time a person experiences the same place, he will recall back to his memory to identify the place and further more to compare the stored information¹⁸. Nevertheless, the question raised here is what is being identified in each place or building as a man experiences a space, and stored as information of memory. To be more specific, it is important to identify what values are recognized and are appreciated by a user so that they can be either preserved or developed in a future transformation of an abandoned industrial building.

Nevertheless, values of an industrial building are countless to be appreciated and developed for a future transformation. The aim is to concentrate to most important ones that are appreciated by the users. Industrial complexes are fascinating buildings and are appreciated by people for not only their containing technology but also for their production of goods and lastly for their architectural value. However these are not the only elements that constitute the memory of an industrial complex as a landmark but also their surrounding landscape and how it is transformed through the years of the factory's operation. By identifying the above essentials for an industrial complex we can create a concept that will be based on the memory as a design strategy. However, the aim of using the memory is not for preserving the building as a museum landmark for its surrounding environment, but the way we can use the memory and turn it into a design strategy. The strategy aims to revitalize an industrial complex step by step, not only to achieve cost efficiency but most importantly for the users and visitors, to accept the change of the building and furthermore of the place. We have to pay attention to the people's connection of memory to place, their sensitivity and respect in the way we are treating a valuable building. By making the people witnesses of this step by step process of transformation, the architect makes them part of the design strategy and gives them the chance to get involved in this process by experiencing it instead of a common preservation that will request the people's acceptance from one day to another.

New functions

Following the strategy of incremental transformation of an industrial complex, the new functions that will be inserted and incorporated to the existing complex require to anticipate the same concept of the memory as the design strategy. As we mentioned above, memory is a subjective element that will affect the design, not as mimesis of its predecessor, but as a development of it. New functions should derive from the previous creating a reference to the past but keeping the memory for the future.

The fact that we are attempting to insert a new program into an existing industrial building by incremental change will require a slow adaption due to gradual and expandable structure from the inside to the outside on the ruins of a memorable building. By this gesture we recognize the building's memory related to previous functions and develop on top of it the new, as an attempt to recycle it. The question then is how one operation of an industrial building could be created or developed into a new one and at the same time relate to the memory of the building's function or production line. The solution then can be generated from the issues that brought an industrial complex into depress and finally closing down. The fact that technology is improved and developed in the ongoing demandable life, industry is called to respond and adapt the new emerge needs and further changes. As result most of the industrial complexes seem unable to respond to these demands, due to their insufficient technology or structure, having as a consequence to end their life¹⁹. The aim of the designers and generally of society is to investigate the issues that brought a factory to its end and generate those that could bring the solution to the previous.

Adaption and Research on Technical Equipment

Industrial Buildings are characterized as historical buildings when they appear to have great architectural value. Nevertheless, today, it is strongly believed and acknowledged that these buildings host also another important cultural component, that of their containment of technical equipment. This cultural component reveals the continuous effort of humans resolving basic needs such as investigation of the solution and improvement of the quality of life. Technical culture is always interwoven with the human evolution and its record and research has become part of the history of technology. We must realize that industrial units with great architecture are the container of a production line with the support of this technological support and the humans as the manager and controller of them. This equipment then could be characterized as the living organism of the building that functions with only purpose the production of goods²⁰.

It will be intelligent then to propose and insert a function that will emerge from the existing, not just to create a relationship with the memory of the building, but also to adapt it either to its containing technology or in general to its former production line. Issues of the building and its products could become interest of investigation and research for further development. The network of this technological equipment can become a great source of understanding not only how this building was functioning and producing goods but also inform for other things such as political, social and financial conditions, working place, rights and legal subjects, environment and ecological conditions, geological conditions and primary sources, etc.

Research on the technical equipment will raise several values such as scientific, technical, structural, aesthetic, ecological and financial²¹.

-Scientific values, as a result of the investigation and application of contemporary knowledge on physics, mathematics, chemistry and other sciences.

-Technical and structural values because of new materials, methods and techniques .

-Aesthetic values due to the appearance of machines that sometimes mimic from nature (snail), where in the newer machines we have variation on colouring, minimization of scale, aerodynamic shapes or extreme shapes that were prototypes for that period.

-Ecological values due to the concern of minimizing blare and emissions, economy on energy, use of dangerous ingredients and recycle materials.

-Financial values with main aim the reduction of cost of production that is basically the main issue for a product production and business viability.

Research in the above fields can give us conclusions and results for further improvement of the industrial world. Creating the proper spaces within an existing industrial building, several labs can be introduced and hosted in order to investigate issues that exist or be created through the factory's function and production in general. This gesture could be characterized as a development of the previous function informing the new one of its future function, preserving the memory of its predecessor.

On the other hand introduction of new uses emerge from the previous, can also achieve a sustainable attitude towards the building's functions by recycling old with new functions and in-relate them. It is a chance also, to take advantage of the container technology of the building for investigation and research, rather than remove them, which again, is much more cost efficient.

New Building Structure:

The concept of incremental change will not only aim for a sustainable attitude in terms of recycling the existing functions of the building, but eventually achieve it on the same way on the building structure. Consequence, instead of preserving the existing fabric with several supports and reinforcement, we allow the building to end its life and step by step deconstruct and replace itself with a contemporary construction that is certainly much more efficient and feasible at the end.

The new strategy describes the incremental deconstruction of the building and its replacement with new construction in order to host the new functions but also reveal in a way, the new parts of the buildings from the existing so it will be noticeable how the slow transformation of the buildings from inside to outside takes place. The strategy stands upon the death of the existing structure where instead of maintain and reinforce the existing building fabric, we let it slowly 'die' ,taking advantage of the last years of its stand, and then eventually deconstruct the dead parts of it and construct the new.

The debate that we are asked to answer is the efficiency of the strategy of not maintaining the existing structure and build on the ruins of it. Feasibility studies show that any maintenance and reinforcement of the building will add to it another 20-30 years of life and the cost of it is double than a normal construction²². By let the building "decompose" and starting incremental construction from inside to outside, the new structure will allow us to adapt the new structure of the building to the new needs, taking advantage of some parts of the building and slowly disband the existing fabric revealing the new one. The new construction will not only provide more years, than the reinforcement structure, but it will also cost much less. Finally, the result will be a contemporary construction that will not only correspond sustainably to the local climate but also technologically support the emerging needs of its future use.

The new parts should correspond to the contemporary standards of construction and they should be flexible, prefabricated and recyclable so they can adapt all the future changes of functions and structure that will emerge in the future, if there is complete change of the program. For example, the new structure could be light-weight such as metal structure and the exterior skin could be from recycled polycarbonate panels²³. The goal is to create a new structure that will not only be flexible and cheap but will also be adaptable to the existing fabric of the building and succeed to incorporate all the sustainable attitudes that a new building requires with passive systems that take advantages of the primary energy sources such as light, air and water.

Nevertheless, the strategy for the new building structure attitude is related to memory where even the new construction should be dealt with a system that will have a process through life and eventually one day will expire (figure 1). As Abalos and Herreros Architects point out that the way that a structure is planned to be constructed and host the new functions, need to take in consideration that one day it will need either to adapt new uses or eventually deconstruct due to the emerging needs of development²⁴. As result, we have to deal with both function and structure as recycled elements that can be transformed or dispatch when the time comes, where they have complete their life cycle.

Figure 1. Strategies for the new building

Incremental Healing of the Surrounding Landscape

The case of the surrounding landscape, where most of the time refers to the Brownfield, which has equal connection with memory as a strategy to deal with. As mention above scars of an industrial complex could be also the polluted soils with toxicity creating an effect of desert around these complexes. The idea is not erase drastically the scars of the landscape due to their relationship with memory of place. These scars can inform and reference to the past of the areas function, and a strategy of incremental transformation should exist.

As result, these scars will originally be incorporated in the new program of the area, but through a step by step transformation of site, these scars will eventually absorb and disappear as a healing process, making again the users testifiers of a journey²⁵. One of the founders of the methodology, Latz architect, explains that the idea of this approach aims to achieve that a grandfather can go through this landscape with his grandchildren and he will be able to explain them the function of the complex by reference to the scarves which are becoming evidences of function. Nevertheless, these scars will start to disappear, they are absorbed through time, and it will project the process of life that goes on recycle through its ashes.

Applications of Incremental Transformation – Sopaz Case Study

Exploring the possibilities of applying the above proposals into a real factory was chosen due to my parallel research in Studio course. Factory Sopaz is an industrial complex located in the capital of Cyprus and currently producing aliment for several animals. Due to the fact that the factory was built in 1970, it deals with issues of infrastructure concerning the technology that supports the production of the factory and also the building fabric that seems to become weaker through the years. Interviewing the general director of the industrial unit admit that the factory left with another 2 years of operation before it will be fall into depress.

As result the company questions the future of the complex where either they will renew it again as factory by upgrading the technological equipment or demolish and sale the property so they can move their industry to a new region outside the city.

My studies reveal the building's architectural and memory value where firstly the building poses a great modern structure, constructed fully of fair face concrete where in the other hand the memory of the building become so strong in area, nominating the building as landmark, resulting to name the whole area with the building's brand. Following the above strategy, my proposal will deal with the building's memory related always with the function of it producing aliment for several animals.

Figure2 . Existing situation of the buildings

Shifting Between Private and Public Circulation

The bond between farmers & scientist

Figure 3. Buildings proposal.

Figure 4. Building proposal

Following then the above issues, a strategy of incremental transformation of the complex should be created considering the new program of the building and how this eventually will be succeeded. The first gesture will deal with the surrounding landscape of the factory using the ‘phytoremediation’ technique in order to start the healing of the surrounding soils. This will also make the first statement to the area for the future transformation of the building.

Nevertheless during the first 2 years, the above process will take place in the complex until it will finally close. The next gesture will deal with the insertion of new uses and further more the new construction. The question then raised is what could be the next use of an industrial building that was producing aliment for animals that can inform and generate a new one? The case study of Charlie’s Chocolate Factory will inform us of how we should generate the new program. Researching on the specific field, I conclude that this kind of industries investigate ways of producing better qualities of aliment for the animals, improving their ingredients so these products can resist through time and the same time provide better aliment enrichment in vitamins. As result of the issue, an institution of research and development of aliment, could be generated in order to investigate and develop new methods of production. Labs of experimentation could be incorporated as new functions but, nevertheless additional construction is required to house these special functions.

Since the new function is generated through the issues of the previous one, the strategy now needs to find ways of incremental adaptive transformation of the building fabric. The first gesture will deal with an addition on a section of the building to host the labs, since the structure of the building has another 10 years of life before the need of reinforce. This action now will be the first statement regarding the building transformation to the surrounding area. The type of the construction then will follow the case study of the Recycle Plant Factory in Spain with light weight structures and polycarbonate panels achieving a sustainable attitude towards the buildings function providing sufficient light and inverse the effect at night, and second, create the proper condition for a future reuse of the structure or further dismantling.

The next step will follow in the next 5 years after the public's acceptance for the new added structure and will be the several services for the workers of the labs such as administration and library. This step now will be followed with the first inner demolitions in order to create to proper spaces for the new functions. In some cases the demolitions will be revealed to the outside of the building fabric and then replaced with the new structure that mention above.

Figure 5. Bioclimatic Design Strategies- natural ventilation and solar exposure

Figure 6. Bioclimatic Design Strategies- natural ventilation

The strategy will continue with expansion of other functions and further demolition in stages in order to host the rest of the program that will included the auxiliary functions like cafeteria and restaurant and finally residences for the students of the institute. Each stage is calculated to be executed approximately every five

years in order to complete in 30 years, since the stages of expansion are six. This will result to a step by step transformation through the years, recycling both function and structure of its predecessor. Eventually the idea deals with the life cycle of the new building since the first gesture will have a difference of 30 years of construction to the last. The design tries to achieve a strategy that will allow the endless phenomenon of the incremental transformation in the complex, even when it completes its transformation, since the structure and function will be recycle due to their expiration of life.

Figure 7. Building proposal

Conclusion:

Historical industrial complexes constitute a unique sample of our industrial heritage, from an architectural, constructional and technological perspective, which they consist of integral pieces of collective memory of cities. Therefore, any design for the exploitation and their management should respect their character and memory. Nevertheless designers and planners should always aim to preserve memory not in the sense of museum but use it as a design strategy that will eventually generate the new proposals for an abandoned industrial building. Consequently, this strategy requires a methodology that with incremental transformation to a place, succeeding to enhance the past with the future, where transformations are executed step by step. This long term gesture finally will result to create a process where people are becoming the testifiers of this change, having the chance to evolve, experience it and finally accept it as part of the memory development. The strategy strives to achieve a sustainable attitude not only towards the building's recycle of use but also through its cost efficiency providing new construction that will host the future use. It in our hands to identify, respect and use the memory as design strategy that will eventually create a formula of proposal, resulting the desirable continuity from the past through the present and the future.

References:

- ¹ Nomikos, Michael. *Re-establishment and reuse of historical buildings and totals, Methodology -Applications*, Aristotelio University of Salonica Press, Department of Architecture, Salonica, Greece, 2004, 76.
- ² Michael Nomikos, *Re-establishment and reuse of historical buildings and totals, Methodology -Applications*, Aristotelio University of Salonica Press, Department of Architecture, Salonica, Greece, 2004, 77-78.
- ³ Michael Nomikos, *Re-establishment and reuse of historical buildings and totals, Methodology -Applications*, Aristotelio University of Salonica Press, Department of Architecture, Salonica, Greece, 2004, 77-78.
- ⁴ George Lavvas, *Protection of Monuments and Totals: Basic Significances, Ideology and Methodology*, Aristotelio University of Salonica Press, Department of Architecture, Salonica, Greece, 1984, 17.
- ⁵ Sherban Cantacuzino, *Re/Architecture: Old Buildings/New Uses*. New York: Abbeville Press, 1989, 23.
- ⁶ AspasiaLouvi, *Viable and compatible uses in old factories*, Poria, Athens, Greece, 2007, 29. ⁷ JohnKizis. *New Architecture in Old Industrial Fabrics*, Poria, Honorary Volume In The professor D.Ziva, Athens, Greece, 2007, 272.
- ⁷ John Kizis. *New Architecture in Old Industrial Fabrics*, Poria, Honorary Volume In The professor D.Ziva, Athens, Greece, 2007, 272.
- ⁸ Christos Marathovouniotis, Regions of Special Characters, *Cyprus Architects Association*, July 2008 Vol. 4/5: 21
- ⁹ AspasiaLouvi, *Viable and compatible uses in old factories*, Poria, Athens, Greece, 2007, 27.
- ¹⁰ Richard Austin, *Adaptive Reuse: Issues and Case Studies in Building Preservation*. David G. Woodcock, W. Cecil Steward, and R. Alan Forrester, editors. New York: Van Nostrand Reinhold Company, 1988, 72.
- ¹¹ JohnKizis. *New Architecture in Old Industrial Fabrics*, Poria, Honorary Volume In The professor D.Ziva, Athens, Greece, 2007, 271.
- ¹² AspasiaLouvi, *Viable and compatible uses in old factories*, Poria, Athens, Greece, 2007, 299. ¹³ Peter Hadjioannou, “Industrial Buildings”, *The Building*, July 210 Vol 6, 109
- ¹³ John Kizis, *New Architecture in Old Industrial Fabrics*, Poria, Honorary Volume In The professor D.Ziva, Athens, Greece, 2007, 275-6.
- ¹⁴ AspasiaLouvi, *Viable and compatible uses in old factories*, Poria, Athens, Greece, 2007, 302.
- ¹⁵ Nomikos, Michael. *Re-establishment and reuse of historical buildings and totals, Methodology -Applications*, Aristotelio University of Salonica Press, Department of Architecture, Salonica, Greece, 2004, 89.
- ¹⁶ Sebastien, Marot, and Architectural Association. *Sub-Urbanism and the Art of Memory*, London: Architectural Association, 2003, 42.
- ¹⁷ Sebastien, Marot, and Architectural Association. *Sub-Urbanism and the Art of Memory*, London: Architectural Association, 2003, 44.
- ¹⁸ William, J, Mitchell. *Placing Words Symbols, Space, and the City*. Cambridge MA: MIT Press, 2005, 8.
- ¹⁹ Aspasia Louvi, *Viable and compatible uses in old factories*, Poria, Athens, Greece, 2007, 209.
- ²⁰ Sakis Hajigoga, “Appointment of Historical Equipment in Industrial Buildings and Monuments of Technical Culture,” *The Building* (June 2008) Vol 173: 117.
- ²¹ Sakis Hajigoga, “Appointment of Historical Equipment in Industrial Buildings and Monuments of Technical Culture,” *The Building* (June 2008) Vol 173: 118-119.
- ²² George Lavvas, *Protection of Monuments and Totals: Basic Significances, Ideology and Methodology*, Aristotelio University of Salonica Press, Department of Architecture, Salonica, Greece, 1984, 34.
- ²³ Andrea, Deplazes. *Constructing Architecture: Materials Processes Structures, A Handbook*, Birkhauser Verlag AG: Basel, 2005, 126.
- ²⁴ Inaki, Abalos. *Recycling Madrid: Abalos and Herreros*, Actar, Barcelona/ES, 2001, 26. ³⁵ Udo, Weilacher. *Syntax of Landscape: The Landscape Architecture by Peter Latz and Partners*. Basel Berlin Boston: Birkhauser Publisher, 2008, 104.
- ²⁵ Udo, Weilacher. *Syntax of Landscape: The Landscape Architecture by Peter Latz and Partners*. Basel Berlin Boston: Birkhauser Publisher, 2008, 105.